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COLLEGE NIRF RANK PREDICTION USING MACHINELEARNING

ABSTRACT:College NIRF rank prediction is useful for predicting the NIRF rankings of the institutes in India. The National Institutional Ranking Framework (NIRF) [1] was approved by the MHRD and the rankings are released every year by the Honourable Minister of Human Resource Development reflecting the performances of various institutes in India. This study uses the power of machine learning algorithms to predict the NIRF rank of the institute based on their score in several features. There are numerous features on which the rankings are released; these features are majorly categorized into five parameters (TLR, Research, GO, PI, Outreach). Predicting NIRF rank will not only help students in their institute selection process but also helps the institute identify their weak areas so that they can improve in those areas. Our study not only predicts the NIRF rank of the institute but also helps the institute to compare their scores with the top institute by entering the rank of the institute with which they want to compare. Predicting NIRF rank can be understood as a regression problem where the rank is the output, there are several regression algorithms such as Linear Regression, Decision Tree, Random forest etc., by using various metrics such as RMSE (root mean square error), mean square error etc. we can select an effective algorithm. Using flask server / Django we have converted the site into an application with a simple user interface.

Keywords: NIRF, machine learning, RMSE, Flask server, Random Forest, Linear regression, Decision Tree.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Machine learning algorithms have been widely studied and used in various domains of education. Dr. Bishnuprasad Mishra and Dr. Banashri Rath [1] proposed a machine learning technique to find the correct weightage for the best result. Nidhi Agarwal and Devendra Tayal [2] proposed a new way to predict how well universities and colleges rank. Nishi Doshi, Samhitha Gundam and Bhaskar Chaudhury [3] discussed a method to help universities and higher educational institutes improve their rankings using techniques like (EDA, Decision Trees etc).

c) Anika Tabassum, Mahamudul Hasan and Shibir Ahmed [4] developed a model which predicts the rankings by analyzing influential global performance indicators. Anuva Goyal, Prem Prakash Vuppuluri [5]: "An Analytical Approach

Towards the Prediction of Undefined Parameters for the National Institutional Ranking Framework" explores a method to predict undefined parameters in the National Institutional Ranking Framework (NIRF) for Higher Education Institutions (HEI's) in India.

3. METHODOLOGY

The methodology for predicting the NIRF rank comprises several important steps. At first, data is collected from various sources (we have taken the dataset from Kaggle) such as Kaggle, etc. The collected data will then undergo severe pre-processing to remove the inconsistencies from data to make it suitable for analysis. The sub

sequent step involves selection of features which can be done with the help of principal component analysis (PCA), we have taken 5 features in our system.

Figure1.Methodology

After selection of the features the dataset is partitioned into training dataset and testing dataset. The next step is model development which involves selection of proper machine learning algorithm. As NIRF rank prediction is a regression problem where the output is the rank we have to select proper regression algorithm using some parametric measures such as (RMSE, MSE)

etc. We have tested some major regression algorithms and selected random forest algorithm due its lower RMSE value. Lower the RMSE value more is the accuracy.

4. EXISTING SYSTEM VS PROPOSED SYSTEM

There are several existing systems to predict the NIRF rank of the institutes in one of the Journal of machine learning research the authors came up with an idea of combining both Machine learning algorithms and SNA (Social Network Analysis). In this paper Research productivity, Teaching effectiveness etc. are some of the parameters taken into consideration for predicting the NIRF rank. Another study in the journal of applied research used DEA (data envelopment analysis) to predict the NIRF rank. This study used parameters such as infrastructure, quality of the faculty etc.

In the study published in journal of Data Science the authors used machine learning algorithms such as gradient boosting to predict the NIRF rank parameters used are perception, research.

The proposed System to predict the NIRF rank of the institute uses a suitable machine learning algorithm to predict the NIRF rank based on the overall score obtained from the 5 parameters. At its core the system would begin from data collection from various sources. This data will then undergo rigorous

preprocessing to make the data suitable for training and testing the model. The algorithm used by the proposed system is Randomforest regression algorithm which is having lower RMSE (root mean square error) among all the

regression algorithms after testing with sampled data. Apart from predicting the nirf rank, we also incorporated an innovative feature allowing the institutes to compare their parametric scores with the institute of their desired rank . On entering the rank of their desired institute institutes can access the comparisons of all 5 parameters which are shown in the form of graphs using plotly library.

5.RESULTS

College NIRF Rank Predictor

The screenshot shows a web form titled "College NIRF Rank Predictor". It contains five input fields for scores: "Teaching, Learning and Resources (TLR) Score" with value 90, "Research and Professional Practice (RPC) Score" with value 87, "Graduation Outcome (GO) Score" with value 40, "Outreach and Inclusivity (OI) Score" with value 65, and "Perception Score" with value 97. Below these is a dropdown menu labeled "Enter the rank to compare with:" with the value "1" selected. A blue "Predict" button is at the bottom.

Figure2. Post-InputFormPicture

Figure3.Outcomeofformsubmission

Now enter the scores of the institution top redictit's NIRF ranking, also enter the NIRF rank of the institution to compare:

Figure4. Comparison of feature values with a specified rank for analysis

Comparison of tlr with Top-Ranked College

Figure5. Comparison of TLR-Teaching, Learning and Resources

Comparison of rpc with Top-Ranked College

Figure6.ComparisonofRPC-ResearchandProfessional Practices

Comparison of go with Top-Ranked College

Figure7.ComparisonofGO-GraduationOutcome

Comparison of oi with Top-Ranked College

Figure8.ComparisonofOI-OutreachandInclusivity.

Comparison of perception with Top-Ranked Colle

Figure9.ComparisonofPerception

6.CONCLUSION

In conclusion this study represents an important application of machine learning algorithms in prediction of NIRF rank of the institutes in India. The NIRF rank prediction not only assists the students in selection of institute but also helps the institute to identify their weak areas and also provides an insights into performance of the institutes to assist policy makers in decision making. Also in this paper we have introduced a new feature allowing the institutes to compare their scores with other institutes. Among the various machine learning algorithms we found out the Random forest regression has lower root mean square value (13.9) among all other regression algorithms. Currently the model has been built with limited features, apparently in future there will more parameters to be incorporated into the model. As the performance of the institute will vary from year to year the model needs to be continuously monitored.

REFERENCES

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